

Managing Editor's Column

Vol. 11, No. 6; June 28, 2005

Dear Readers:

It is with pleasure that I present to you this month's extensive issue of 16 excellent papers that show the range of subjects covered by J.UCS. The issue also shows the international flavour of our journal: the contributions come from 16 countries! Those are, in alphabetical order: Australia, Austria, China, Czech Republic, Egypt, Greece, India, Iran, Italy, Japan, New Zealand, Pakistan, The Netherlands, Tunisia, United Arab Emirates and the USA!

I am sure you will find a number of contributions that will interest you. Please continue to help J.UCS to grow, by submitting high quality papers and recommending our journal to your friends.

Note also that Volume 10 (2004) is now also available in printed form, with 1733 pages (!) the largest volume so far! To order the archive edition, please fax or send us the order form from http://www.jucs.org/jucs_subscription/print.html

Finally, I'd like to draw your attention to the launch of two new journals: Journal of Universal Knowledge Management (<http://www.jukm.org>) and Journal of Universal Science and Technology of Learning (<http://www.justl.org>) which will be published by the same team as is responsible for the publication of J.UCS. Because of the immensely growing interest for publication in J.UCS, we have lately not been able to provide the necessary publication space for all authors and guest editors interested in publishing their articles in our journal. To alleviate this problem and to provide new platforms for the dynamic areas of Knowledge Management and E-Learning, the new journals were established and will be opened for submissions in August 2005 and September 2005, respectively. If you are interested in publication, membership of the editorial board or any other aspect connected with the new journals, please contact the two managing editors, namely Klaus Tochtermann (J.UKM) at ktochter@know-center.at or Heinz Dreher (J.USTL) at hdreher@iicm.edu. We look forward to hearing from you!

For now - enjoy reading this 'special' regular issue!

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
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